

Compliance Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around compliance risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 1999 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Compliance Risk". Based on the search results, there were 112 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to compliance risk is divided into 14 clusters and 87 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 6 main themes related to compliance risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Compliance Risk; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Literature Review; Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

INTRODUCTION

Risk management in financial institutions has improved in line with developments in the financial industry as a whole. In recent years, financial institutions have begun to understand the importance of risk management to maintain business stability and continuity. This can be seen from the existence of regulations from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which regulate risk exposure management and effective corporate governance. Risks in the financial sector must be recognized and controlled by estimating the potential that may occur in the future, not after the risk has already occurred. Therefore, a methodology for modeling risks that may occur in the future is very important so that those making decisions can prepare strategies to overcome future risk. One of the risks that occur in the financial industry is compliance risk. Compliance risk management involves identifying, assessing, controlling and monitoring these risks over time to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains its reputation.

In previous research, the development of compliance risk in banking has increased in recent years. This is due to changes in regulations and public demands for transparency and accountability in the financial industry. Banks also experience serious consequences if they violate regulations, such as sanctions and damaged reputations. The Bank also complies with applicable rules and regulations, such as Anti-Money Laundering (AML) regulations, Personal Data Protection (PDP) regulations, and other regulations. Banks must also ensure that their business practices are fair and transparent, and do not harm customers or other parties. In an effort to avoid compliance risks, several banks implement strict systems and procedures, as well as train their staff to understand and comply with applicable regulations. Technological developments and business innovations such as financial technology (fintech) bring new challenges for banks in managing compliance risks. Banks must continue to adapt and ensure that they comply with applicable regulations and ensure good business practices. This requires collaboration between banks and the government to ensure adequate regulations and in accordance with existing business developments. Therefore, banks are now more focused on ensuring that they comply with all applicable regulations and ensure that their business practices do not harm consumers or other parties, so that banks can ensure integrity and public trust in the financial industry.

Based on the problems above, it is necessary to map compliance risk management topics to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for

human resources tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around compliance risks in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) literature review study to analyze, identify and review articles from indexed international journals and accredited national journals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Compliance risk is the risk associated with violating or not complying with regulations, rules, laws and standards that apply to the banking sector. This could involve breaches of banking regulations, anti-money laundering regulations, and personal data protection regulations. Compliance risks can also stem from failure to adhere to industry standards or widely accepted best practices. Compliance is important for the banking sector because it ensures that financial institutions operate in a fair, transparent manner and in accordance with applicable regulations. Compliance risk also helps to prevent unethical or detrimental business practices, such as money laundering or other illegal activities.

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature. Some applications of bibliometric studies include citation network analysis, cluster analysis, and visibility analysis. Results from bibliometric studies can be used by researchers, government, and industry to understand developments and contributions in scientific fields and to determine future research directions.

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature. It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently.

Literature review is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions. Literature review studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment and produce non-duplicative results. It also helps in determining problems and gaps in the existing literature and helps in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas. Literature review studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Literature review studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review

studies. The object of the research is compliance risk. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on compliance risks in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions.

The source of data collection comes from search for national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and Harzing via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keyword " Compliance Risk " in the entire year period (1999 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics research based on literature review studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Compliance Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 112 international and national journals based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1999 to 2022. There are 22 journals Scopus indexed international. And there is 90 international and national journals indexed by Sinta around compliance risk research.

Table 1: Journal publication data regarding Compliance Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1999	1	2005	2	2011	3	2017	9
2000	1	2006	4	2012	3	2018	6
2001	1	2007	4	2013	5	2019	11
2002	1	2008	3	2014	5	2020	10
2003	-	2009	8	2015	8	2021	11
2004	-	2010	1	2016	7	2022	8

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Compliance Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1: Network visualization of a map of research developments around Compliance Risk. Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research development map regarding Compliance Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, there are 14 clusters and 87 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 9 topic items, namely: customer, Indonesia, Islamic rural bank, Islamic rural customers, loyalty, risk perception, service quality, sharia compliance, trust.
- Cluster 2, consists of 8 topic items, namely: accounting, banking, compliance risk management, diversified environment, financial services roundtable, morin center, regulation, securities industry.
- Cluster 3, consists of 8 topic items, namely: bank risk, Basel core principle, Canadian banking, effective banking supervision, evolution, risk compliance, risk executive, strategic risk.
- Cluster 4 consists of 7 topic items, namely: bank regulation, compliance, compliance failure, expectations, internal audit, private banking, risk management.
- Cluster 5, consists of 7 topic items, namely: bank regulation, central bank, compliance function, internal control system, Italian banking sector, Latvia, operational risk.
- Cluster 6, consists of 7 topic items, namely: compliance risk assessment, Islamic bank, non-compliance, profitability, rate, return, sharia compliance risk.
- Cluster 7, consists of 6 topic items, namely: Africa, banking sector, compliance management, Pakistan, regulatory compliance, risk assessment.
- Cluster 8, consists of 6 topic items, namely: bpr, sharia banking, risk mitigation, sharia, sharia, tbk.
- Cluster 9, consists of 6 topic items, namely: banking industry, devastation, hurricane Katrina, legal risk, post Katrina world, south Africa.
- Cluster 10, consists of 6 topic items, namely: bank, legal, risk management, reputation, risk management system, tax compliance risk.
- Cluster 11, consists of 5 topic items, namely: banking business model, Basel Accord membership, international banking risk, relations, WTO.
- Cluster 12, consists of 5 topic items, namely: bank performance, effectiveness, financial performance, governance, guidelines.

- Cluster 13, consists of 4 topic items, namely: Bank Islam Malaysia Berhad, compliance risk, monitoring, sharia non compliance.
- Cluster 14 consists of 3 topic items, namely: business, company, risk.

Mapping Literature Review around the Definition and Objectives of Compliance Risk Management

First, the definition of compliance risk, namely the risk associated with violations of the rules, regulations and standards applicable in the banking industry. This includes the risk that banks will not comply with anti-money laundering regulations, privacy regulations, applicable trading regulations, and many others. The consequences of these violations can include legal and financial sanctions, reputational harm, and business loss. Therefore, banks must ensure that they have adequate systems and procedures to ensure compliance with all applicable rules and regulations to minimize compliance risks.

Second, the aim of compliance risk management, namely to ensure that the bank's business activities comply with applicable rules, regulations and legislation. This includes the task of monitoring and identifying potential compliance risks, ensuring that the bank has adequate procedures and systems to address compliance risks, and ensuring that bank staff understand and comply with applicable regulations. Some of the main objectives of compliance risk management in banking include: (1) Maintaining business integrity, namely by ensuring that the bank complies with applicable regulations and legislation, compliance risk management helps maintain the integrity of the bank's business; (2) Avoiding sanctions, namely banks must comply with applicable rules and regulations to avoid sanctions, such as fines or penalties, from the regulator; (3) Maintaining business reputation, namely banks must ensure that their business practices meet the standards set by regulators and the public; and (4) Increasing business efficiency, namely compliance risk management ensuring that the bank has adequate procedures and systems to overcome compliance risks, thereby helping to increase business efficiency.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Compliance Risk Monitoring

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the authority and responsibility of the Board of Commissioners. The following are some of the duties and authorities of the Board of Commissioners in terms of compliance risk: (1) Responsible for ratifying compliance policies and procedures that must be adhered to by bank staff; (2) monitor the implementation of compliance policies and ensure that bank staff understand and comply with applicable regulations; (3) understand and monitor the compliance risks faced by the bank and ensure that the bank has procedures and systems to overcome these risks; (4) ensure that the bank has an adequate internal monitoring system and ensure that bank staff report detected compliance risks; and (5) ensure that the bank takes necessary actions to correct compliance problems and ensure that such problems do not occur again.

Second, the authority and responsibility of the Board of Directors. Here are some of them: (1) Defining and establishing banking strategies related to compliance risk, including determining priorities and risk tolerance levels; (2) Establish a pattern of compliance actions and procedures, and ensure that staff and subsidiaries understand and comply with them; (3) Monitor and control compliance risks, including taking corrective action if there are violations or failures to comply with compliance patterns and procedures; (4) Ensure that banks have systems and procedures to report violations and monitor developments in this regard; (5) Determine budgets and allocate resources to ensure that banks have effective systems and procedures to manage and control compliance risks; and (6) Recruit, monitor and evaluate staff and contractors responsible for duties and responsibilities related to compliance risks.

Third, related to Human Resources (HR), namely:

- (1) HR is an important factor in ensuring banking compliance. Employees and officers in banking play a key role in ensuring that the bank complies with applicable rules and regulations. Compliance risks in banking can occur if employees or employees

do not understand or comply with applicable rules and regulations. Therefore, continuous training and education is very important for HR to ensure they understand the applicable rules and regulations, as well as ensure that they follow the right procedures in carrying out their duties.

- (2) Clear and open policies and procedures are also critical in ensuring compliance. Open policies and procedures help employees and employees understand their duties and responsibilities, and ensure that they follow appropriate procedures in carrying out their duties.
- (3) A good monitoring and evaluation system is also very important to ensure compliance. Banks must have a system for monitoring and evaluating the duties and activities of employees and officers, and ensuring that they comply with applicable rules and regulations.

Fourth, related to the Compliance Risk Management Organization (Compliance Risk Management Organization), which is the part of the banking organization that is responsible for ensuring that bank operations comply with applicable rules and regulations. The goal is to prevent non-compliant actions and protect banks from potential losses caused by violations of laws and regulations. The Compliance Risk Management Organization has duties such as: (1) Determining and monitoring the rules and regulations that apply to banks; (2) Carrying out an assessment of compliance risks and making plans to minimize these risks; (3) Providing training and education for bank staff regarding applicable rules and regulations; (4) Recommend changes in bank operating procedures and patterns to ensure compliance with rules and regulations; and (5) Oversee the implementation of programs and procedures to ensure consistency and effectiveness.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Strategy, Risk Level, Policies, Procedures and Limits in Compliance Risk Management

First, compliance risk management strategy. Compliance risk management strategies in banking have several main objectives, such as ensuring that banks comply with applicable rules and regulations, minimizing legal and reputation risks, and ensuring the integrity of banking businesses and operations. The following are several compliance risk management strategies that can be used by banks: (1) identifying risks that may arise which may involve reviewing applicable regulations and conducting internal evaluations; (2) Once a risk is identified, the bank must have an effective response plan to overcome the risk, if it occurs. This plan should ensure that the bank has clear procedures to ensure that regulations and rules are implemented; (3) Training and sensitization are essential to ensure that banking employees and leaders understand compliance risks and have the knowledge of how to perform their duties in a compliant manner; (4) Banks must monitor and evaluate their performance periodically to ensure that they comply with regulations and rules. It also ensures that the response plan is functioning properly and the bank is prepared to address possible risks; and (5) Banks must work closely with regulators to ensure that they understand the applicable rules and regulations and that they have clear procedures to ensure that regulations are implemented.

Second, the level of risk to be taken (Risk Appetite) and risk tolerance (Risk Tolerance) for compliance risk. Risk Appetite and Risk Tolerance are concepts that are often used in risk management to measure and manage potential risks that may occur. In the context of compliance risk in banking, these two concepts have an important meaning and role. Risk Appetite is the amount of risk that a company, including banking, is expected and willing to take. It describes the maximum limit of risk that a company can accept to achieve its goals. Risk Appetite will differ between companies and can be influenced by factors such as business strategy, long-term goals, and level of financial stability. Risk Tolerance, on the other hand, refers to the maximum level of risk that a company can accept in terms of compliance risk. It shows the extent to which companies are willing to take risks and take action to ensure that their business activities do not violate applicable laws and regulations. In banking, compliance risk is the risk that a company will not meet applicable regulatory requirements, such as anti-money laundering regulations and privacy

regulations. Because these risks are very important to ensure the integrity and reputation of the company, the Risk Tolerance for compliance risks is usually very low.

Third, compliance risk policy. Compliance risk policy (compliance risk policy) is part of banking risk management which aims to ensure that banking complies with applicable regulations and regulations, including banking, taxation, environmental and human rights regulations. This helps banks to avoid potential government sanctions, lawsuits, and reputational harm. This policy includes procedures and actions that must be taken by banks to ensure that they always operate within the limits of applicable regulations. This includes: (1) Identification and assessment of compliance risks, including regulatory, legal and regulatory risks; (2) Planning and implementing an effective compliance program; (3) Training and education for banking staff regarding applicable regulations and regulations; (4) Monitoring and control system to ensure that banks continue to comply with applicable regulations; and (5) Procedures for investigating and handling cases of regulatory violations. This policy also determines the responsibilities and authority of individuals in banking to ensure that banking always operates within the limits of applicable regulations.

Fourth, compliance risk procedures. Compliance risk in banking is a potential risk arising from violations of banking regulations, tax regulations, data protection regulations and other applicable regulations. Procedures for managing compliance risk in banking include the following steps:

- (1) Identify risks. The first step in managing compliance risk is risk identification. This is done through a deep understanding of applicable regulations and how banks may be exposed to compliance risks.
- (2) Risk assessment. Once risks are identified, banks must assess the level of risk associated with each risk. This is done through data analysis and risk assessment.
- (3) Risk management strategy planning. Once the risk is assessed, the bank must create a strategic plan to manage the risk. This may include implementing new processes and procedures, improving education and training, or tighter monitoring.
- (4) Strategy implementation. After the strategic plan is created, the bank must implement the strategy by ensuring that all necessary procedures and systems are functioning properly.
- (5) Evaluation and control. Banks must carry out regular evaluations and controls to ensure that compliance risk management strategies are functioning properly. It also ensures that the bank continuously monitors risks and takes necessary actions to address risks as they arise.

Fifth, limit compliance risk. To limit compliance risks in the banking sector, several actions that can be taken are: (1) Banks must establish clear standards and procedures to ensure that they comply with all applicable regulations and rules; (2) Banks must ensure that their staff understand and comply with all applicable regulations and rules, through continuous training and sensibilization; (3) Banks must have an effective internal supervision and control system to ensure that they comply with all applicable regulations and rules; (4) Banks must determine sanctions for staff or units who violate applicable regulations and rules, to ensure that compliance measures are taken seriously; and (5) Banks must conduct regular evaluation and testing to ensure that their systems and procedures are effective in limiting compliance risks.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Identification, Measurement, Monitoring, Control and Compliance Risk Information Systems

First, identify compliance risks. There are several ways to identify compliance risks in banking, including: (1) Banks must carry out an analysis of applicable regulations and regulations to ensure that they understand and comply with applicable regulations; (2) Banks must review systems and procedures to ensure that they have strong and effective compliance procedures; (3) Banks must conduct business risk analysis to determine how compliance risks may affect their business; (4) Banks must collect data from various sources, such as regulatory reports, financial reports, and audit reports, to help identify

compliance risks; (5) Banks must carry out regular monitoring and evaluation of their compliance programs and procedures to ensure that they comply with applicable rules and regulations; (6) Banks can consult on compliance risks with experts who understand banking rules and regulations, to ensure that they understand and comply with applicable regulations; and (7) Banks must ensure that their staff understand compliance risks and how to address these risks, through ongoing training and sensibilization.

Second, measuring compliance risk. Measuring compliance risk in banking is a process to determine the level of risk that bank activities will not comply with applicable rules, regulations and standards. It aims to ensure that banks operate within legal boundaries and minimize legal and reputational risks. The following are several steps in measuring compliance risk in banking: (1) Banks must understand the rules and regulations that apply to their activities, including anti-money laundering regulations, data protection regulations, and consumer protection regulations; (2) Banks must evaluate each activity to determine the level of compliance risk that may be associated with the activity; (3) Banks must ensure that appropriate procedures and internal controls are in place to minimize compliance risks; (4) Banks must carry out regular monitoring to ensure that procedures and internal controls function properly and conduct periodic audits to ensure that rules and regulations are adhered to; (5) Banks must ensure that their staff understand the applicable rules and regulations and have the necessary skills to ensure compliance; (6) Banks must carry out regular measurements and monitoring to ensure that compliance risks remain within acceptable limits and take action if necessary; and (7) Banks must continuously improve and update their procedures and internal controls to ensure that compliance risks remain within acceptable limits.

Third, monitoring compliance risks. Compliance risk monitoring in banking is a process carried out to ensure that banks comply with applicable rules and regulations and ensure that their business practices do not harm certain parties or society in general. The following are several steps that can be taken in monitoring compliance risk in banking: (1) Identification of compliance risk involves identifying applicable rules and regulations and determining how banks can comply with these regulations; (2) Compliance system evaluation involves reviewing existing processes and procedures to ensure that banks comply with applicable rules and regulations; (3) Monitoring business activities involves observing transactions and business activities carried out by banks to ensure that they comply with applicable rules and regulations; (4) Compliance reports involve submitting periodic reports to the competent authorities on how banks comply with applicable rules and regulations; and (5) Compliance training involves training banking employees on applicable rules and regulations and how to ensure that their business practices comply with those regulations.

Fourth, control compliance risk. Controlling compliance risk in banking requires integration and coordination of various functions and departments within the bank. The following are several ways that can be used to control compliance risk in banking: (1) Banks must establish clear policies and procedures to ensure that compliance with applicable rules and regulations is followed properly; (2) Banks must provide education and training for their employees regarding applicable rules and regulations, as well as how they must ensure that their statements and actions meet compliance standards; (3) Banks must regularly monitor and evaluate the implementation of compliance policies and procedures to ensure that they are effective and up-to-date; (4) Banks must have an effective reporting system to report any violations or potential violations of compliance; (5) Banks must conduct regular internal audits to ensure that compliance with applicable rules and regulations is properly followed; and (6) Banks must cooperate with regulators and comply with their requests properly to ensure that compliance with applicable rules and regulations is followed.

Fifth, the Compliance Risk Management Information System (Compliance Risk Management Information System) is a system used by banks to monitor and manage compliance risks with applicable rules, regulations and legislation. This aims to ensure that the bank meets all regulatory requirements and minimizes the risk of criminal acts and

possible losses. This system can perform tasks such as: (1) Monitoring applicable rules and regulations and ensuring that banks comply with all requirements; (2) Detect and report potential compliance risks; (3) Carrying out internal audits and monitoring external audit results reports; (4) Provide reports and analysis of compliance risks; and (5) Evaluate and implement procedures and controls to ensure consistency with regulations. By using a Compliance Risk Management Information System, banks can ensure that they meet all regulatory requirements and minimize the risk of criminal acts and losses. It also helps banks to maintain their reputation and ensure the safety and security of customer funds.

Sixth, Compliance Risk Internal Control System. The Compliance Risk Internal Control System is a control process carried out by banks to ensure that the bank complies with applicable regulations and minimizes compliance risks. This includes procedures and processes that ensure banks follow banking regulations, anti-money laundering (AML) regulations, and data protection regulations. Internal control involves several stages, including risk identification, risk evaluation, development of control plans, implementation of controls, and evaluation of control effectiveness. In this process, banks can also assign responsibilities and duties to employees to ensure the desired level of compliance. The aim of the compliance risk internal control system is to ensure the bank complies with applicable regulations and ensures the security and integrity of the business. It also helps banks avoid sanctions and financial losses that may occur due to non-compliance. Thus, a compliance risk internal control system is very important for banking and is an important part of overall risk management. Banks should conduct regular evaluations and make changes to their systems as necessary to ensure ongoing effectiveness and compliance.

Mapping Literature Review around Problems in Compliance Risk

There are several findings in this research topic, including:

First, the urgency of differentiating tax policies based on compliance risk is to maximize effectiveness and efficiency in achieving tax collection objectives. By paying attention to the compliance risks of each taxpayer, the government can adjust the level of supervision and audit intensity in accordance with these risks. The government can also take preventive action to overcome tax compliance problems, such as providing technical assistance and support to taxpayers, or providing better information and education about tax obligations. This will help strengthen taxpayers' awareness and responsibility to fulfill their obligations. The government can also focus supervision and audit efforts on sectors or groups of taxpayers that have a higher compliance risk. This will help reduce the level of tax leakage and ensure that taxpayers who fulfill their obligations are not favored by non-compliant taxpayers.

Second, the risk of sharia compliance in Islamic sukuk/bonds can come from various sources, such as internal problems of the sukuk issuer, regulatory problems, or market problems. Some examples of sharia compliance risks in sukuk include: (1) Internal problems of the sukuk issuer, namely the sukuk issuer may not meet sharia standards in terms of asset management or business activities; (2) Regulatory issues, namely there are regulatory obstacles that may affect the sukuk's compliance with sharia principles, such as regulations that limit the use of funds or certain business activities; (3) Market problems, namely poor market conditions or changes in economic trends can affect the sukuk's compliance with sharia principles. To overcome sharia compliance risks in sukuk, sukuk issuers must conduct careful due diligence and follow best practices in terms of management and supervision of invested assets. They must also cooperate with regulatory authorities and sharia experts to ensure that their sukuk comply with applicable sharia principles.

Mapping Literature Review around Compliance Risk Management

There are several findings in this research topic, including:

First, Compliance Risk Management (CRM) is a method used to manage and minimize risks associated with non-compliance with laws, regulations and policies within an organization. A CRM engine is an integrated approach to managing compliance risk that

includes a combination of technology, processes and people. The goal of a CRM engine is to help organizations achieve and maintain compliance with laws, regulations, and policies while minimizing the risks associated with non-compliance. The basic steps in the CRM engine process are as follows:

- (1) The first step is to identify the various compliance risks faced by an organization. This may include risks related to laws, regulations, policies and industry standards.
- (2) Assess Risk. The next step is to assess the likelihood and impact of each identified risk. This helps organizations prioritize their compliance efforts and allocate resources effectively.
- (3) Based on the risk assessment, the organization must develop a compliance plan that explains the steps it will take to manage the identified risks. The plan should include a description of the controls to be implemented and the responsibilities of the various stakeholders.
- (4) The next step is to implement a compliance plan, which usually involves implementing technology, processes, and people to manage the identified risks.
- (5) Organizations must regularly monitor their compliance activities to ensure that they are effective in managing risks and achieving desired outcomes. This includes regular reviews and audits of existing controls, as well as tracking the results of risk assessments.
- (6) The final step is to review and improve the CRM engine on an ongoing basis. This includes updating compliance plans, risk assessments, and controls according to changes in the organization's regulatory environment or business operations.

Second, compliance risk in Murabahah, Mudharabah and Ijarah financing in banking is a risk that arises due to customers not fulfilling the obligations stated in the financing contract. Some examples of compliance risks in Murabahah, Mudharabah and Ijarah financing include: (1) Murabahah compliance risk, namely in Murabahah financing, compliance risk occurs if the debtor does not pay the installments according to the predetermined schedule; (2) Mudharabah compliance risk, namely in Mudharabah financing, compliance risk occurs if the fund manager (bank) does not receive the appropriate share of the profits obtained; and (3) Ijarah compliance risk, namely in Ijarah financing, compliance risk occurs if the customer does not pay the rental according to a predetermined schedule or does not return the asset after the rental period ends. To overcome compliance risks in Murabahah, Mudharabah and Ijarah financing, banks can take various actions, such as evaluating risks related to debtors, ensuring that financing contracts include all things necessary to guarantee debtor compliance, and carrying out intensive monitoring and supervision of debtor compliance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding compliance risks in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions during the period 1999 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 112 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding compliance risks in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions are divided into 14 clusters and 87 items. Cluster 1 consists of 9 topics, cluster 2 consists of 8 topics, cluster 3 consists of 8 topics, cluster 4 consists of 7 topics, cluster 5 consists of 7 topics, cluster 6 consists of 7 topics, cluster 7 consists of 6 topics, cluster 8 consists of 6 topics, cluster 9 consists of 6 topics, cluster 10 consists of 6 topics, cluster 11 consists of 5 topics, cluster 12 consists of 5 topics, cluster 13 consists of 4 topics, cluster 14 consists of 3 topics.
- Based on a literature review, there are 6 main research themes surrounding compliance risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely: (1) Definition and objectives of risk management; (2) Risk Supervision; (3) Strategy, risk level, policies, procedures, limits; (4) Identification, measurement,

monitoring, control, information systems; (5) Other problems; and (6) Risk management.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

REFERENCES

- [Sahni, S.](#) and [Singh Kaurav, R.P.](#) (2023), "What? Why? When? How? Where? of Technology-Based Bibliometric Review", [Rana, S., Singh, J. and Kathuria, S.](#) (Ed.) *Advancing Methodologies of Conducting Literature Review in Management Domain (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 2)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 79-101. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520230000002005>
- [Anlesinya, A.](#) and [Dadzie, S.A.](#) (2023), "Technology and the Conduct of Bibliometric Literature Reviews in Management: The Software Tools, Benefits, and Challenges", [Rana, S., Singh, J. and Kathuria, S.](#) (Ed.) *Advancing Methodologies of Conducting Literature Review in Management Domain (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 2)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 57-78. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520230000002004>
- [Mulet-Forteza, C., Genovart-Balaguer, J. and Horrach-Rosselló, P.](#) (2022), "Bibliometric Studies in the Hospitality and Tourism Field: A Guide for Researchers", [Okumus, F., Rasoolimanesh, S.M. and Jahani, S.](#) (Ed.) *Contemporary Research Methods in Hospitality and Tourism*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 55-76. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80117-546-320221005>
- [Ülker, P., Ülker, M. and Karamustafa, K.](#) (2023), "Bibliometric analysis of bibliometric studies in the field of tourism and hospitality", *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 797-818. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-10-2021-0291>
- [Song, Y. and Cao, J.](#) (2022), "An ARIMA-based study of bibliometric index prediction", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 74 No. 1, pp. 94-109. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-03-2021-0072>
- [Akhil, M.P.](#) (2022), "Employing Bibliometric Analysis to Identify Emerging Technologies in the Insurance Industry", [Sood, K., Balusamy, B., Grima, S. and Marano, P.](#) (Ed.) *Big Data Analytics in the Insurance Market (Emerald Studies in Finance, Insurance, and Risk Management)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 207-220. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80262-637-720221011>
- [Ahuja, D., Bhardwaj, P. and Madan, P.](#) (2023), "Money Laundering: A Bibliometric Review of Three Decades from 1990 to 2021", [Tyagi, P., Grima, S., Sood, K., Balamurugan, B., Özen, E. and Eleftherios, T.](#) (Ed.) *Smart Analytics, Artificial Intelligence and Sustainable Performance Management in a Global Digitalised Economy (Contemporary Studies in Economic and Financial Analysis, Vol. 110B)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 55-72. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1569-37592023000110B003>
- [Güngör Göksu, G.](#) (2023), "A retrospective overview of the Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting and Financial Management using bibliometric analysis", *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management*, Vol. 35 No. 2, pp. 264-295. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBAFM-04-2022-0061>

- [Wani, J.A.](#), [Ganaie, S.A.](#) and [Rehman, I.U.](#) (2023), "Mapping research output on library and information science research domain in South Africa: a bibliometric visualisation", *Information Discovery and Delivery*, Vol. 51 No. 2, pp. 194-212. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-10-2021-0115>
- [Ralph, A.](#) and [Arora, A.](#) (2023), "A bibliometric study of reference literature on youth unemployment", *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, Vol. 17 No. 6, pp. 1338-1367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-04-2022-0062>
- [Ryan, J.C.](#) (2021), "Retaining, resigning and firing: bibliometrics as a people analytics tool for examining research performance outcomes and faculty turnover", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 50 No. 5, pp. 1316-1335. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-12-2019-0676>
- [Mokhtari, H.](#), [Barkhan, S.](#), [Haseli, D.](#) and [Saberli, M.K.](#) (2021), "A bibliometric analysis and visualization of the Journal of Documentation: 1945–2018", *Journal of Documentation*, Vol. 77 No. 1, pp. 69-92. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-08-2019-0165>
- [Farooq, R.](#) (2024), "A review of knowledge management research in the past three decades: a bibliometric analysis", *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, Vol. 54 No. 2, pp. 339-378. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-08-2021-0169>
- [Siddique, N.](#), [Ur Rehman, S.](#), [Ahmad, S.](#), [Abbas, A.](#) and [Khan, M.A.](#) (2023), "Library and information science research in the Arab World: a bibliometric analysis 1951–2021", *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, Vol. 72 No. 1/2, pp. 138-159. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-06-2021-0103>
- [Islam, M.A.](#) and [Widen, G.](#) (2023), "Bibliometric analysis of the VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems: 2000–2020", *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, Vol. 53 No. 3, pp. 467-490. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-07-2020-0126>
- [Perannagari, K.T.](#) and [Gupta, S.](#) (2022), "Mapping the Intellectual Structure of Artificial Neural Network Research in Business Domain: A Retrospective Overview Using Bibliometric Review", [Rana, S.](#), [Sakshi](#) and [Singh, J.](#) (Ed.) *Exploring the Latest Trends in Management Literature (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 1)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 35-59. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520220000001003>
- [Davidescu, A.A.](#), [Hapau, R.G.](#) and [Manta, E.M.](#) (2022), "Impact of Crises on Capital Market Volatility: A Bibliometric Analysis", [Grima, S.](#), [Özen, E.](#) and [Boz, H.](#) (Ed.) *The New Digital Era: Other Emerging Risks and Opportunities (Contemporary Studies in Economic and Financial Analysis, Vol. 109B)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 21-53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1569-37592022000109B003>
- [Ali, Q.](#), [Parveen, S.](#), [Aspiranti, T.](#), [Nurhayati, N.](#) and [Rusgianto, S.](#) (2023), "Barriers to the adoption of Islamic banking: a bibliometric analysis", *International Journal of Ethics and Systems*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOES-01-2023-0001>
- [Kumar, S.](#), [Goyal, P.](#), [Kumar, V.](#) and [Vandana](#), (2022), "Cultural Diversity in Tourism: A Bibliometric Analysis of 33 Years (1988–2021)", [Rana, S.](#), [Sakshi](#) and [Singh, J.](#) (Ed.) *Exploring the Latest Trends in Management Literature (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 1)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 147-168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520220000001008>
- [Chhtrapati, D.](#), [Trivedi, D.](#), [Chaudhari, S.P.](#), [Sharma, A.](#) and [Bhatt, A.](#) (2024), "Global research performance on social media security: a bibliometric visualization

analysis", *Information Discovery and Delivery*, Vol. 52 No. 1, pp. 101-113.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-04-2022-0029>